

IMPETUS FAQ

Last updated on February 24th 2023

General

What is IMPETUS?

IMPETUS is a project funded by the European Commission to support and give recognition to citizen science in Europe.

IMPETUS' goal is to

- enable more diverse citizen science initiatives to access funding;
- bring citizen science closer to society and policy makers;
- acknowledge the role of citizen science in tackling the greatest challenges of our times; and
- enable citizen science initiatives to contribute to Green Deal and UN Sustainable Development Goal commitments.

IMPETUS will do this by directly **funding and supporting citizen science initiatives** selected through open calls; awarding the **European Union Prize for Citizen Science** to outstanding projects; and developing **resources that help citizen science initiatives** become more impactful and sustainable.

This open accelerator call is for **funding and support for citizen science initiatives**. IMPETUS is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme. It is delivered by [Zabala](#), [King's College London](#), [Science for Change](#), [T6 Ecosystems srl](#), [EUSEA](#), [Ars Electronica](#), and [Nesta UK](#). It started in July 2022 and will run until June 2026.

What is citizen science?

IMPETUS takes an inclusive view on citizen science. We broadly follow the [Green Paper on Citizen Science for Europe](#) from January 2014, which defines it as the public participating *“in scientific research activities, when citizens actively contribute to science either with their intellectual effort or surrounding knowledge or with their tools and resources.”*

The term covers a range of activities with different levels of participation, from data collection in projects led by trained scientists, to co-designing research questions and policy, to science literacy and public engagement. To truly be considered citizen science it is important that projects have the intention to contribute to research, to produce new research-based knowledge, and for their activities to be carried out by participating citizens. Citizen participation is inherent to citizen science projects and their goals.

Citizen science engages volunteers in a range of scientific activities. This helps educate and inform citizens in the subject matter and leads to greater public understanding of how science and scientists work. Participation in citizen science can increase trust in science and expert opinions, enhance critical thinking, and ultimately fight misinformation, disinformation and fake news. Scientists can learn from citizen science about what people genuinely care about, the impact their work has or should have in society, and become more participatory, by involving volunteers early on in co-designing the research, collecting, cleaning, and analysing the data, documenting the results, and sharing the recognition.

While inclusive, various types of relevant activities are not citizen science. For example: for us it is important that there is a scientific question and methodology, and that the activities are *carried out by* participating citizens.

Competition

What is it about?

IMPETUS is seeking to partner with:

- citizen science projects that want to contribute to measuring progress against sustainable development goals (SDGs);
- new citizen science projects that need support and funding to get off the ground;
- ongoing citizen science projects looking for support and resources to grow and become sustainable;
- communities interested in co-designing research in relevant disciplines;
- organisations in the public, private and third sectors exploring the use of citizen science in their work.

We are looking to fund and support citizen science initiatives tackling one of our two challenges:

- 1) Citizen Science for a Healthy Planet
- 2) Cities for Life

IMPETUS will provide support and funding for a six-month pilot, alongside dedicated acceleration activities, resources and tools to set up and run the pilot. You will have access to a dedicated support programme, as well as a community of like-minded initiatives, tackling similar challenges and contributing to common aims.

How many calls will you have?

IMPETUS runs three open calls, between January and March in 2023, 2024, and 2025. The dates may change slightly. This FAQ is for the first open call only.

When does the call open?

10th January 2023, noon Brussels time

When does the second call close?

13th March 2023, noon Brussels time

How much funding is available?

IMPETUS will award a total of 2,25 million Euros in funding across all open calls. Funds are divided between kickstarting projects, funded at 20,000€ each, and sustaining projects, funded at 10,000€ each.

In this first open call, we aim to allocate 650,000€.

How many pilots will be funded?

Overall, IMPETUS aims to fund 100 kickstarting projects and 25 sustaining projects. For this first open call, we aim to recruit 30 kickstarting and 5 sustaining projects, though numbers may differ slightly depending on applications received.

How do I apply?

Follow the instructions from <https://impetus4cs.eu/>

Eligibility

How do I know if I am eligible to apply?

Refer to the information outlined in our '[Guide for Applicants](#)', or our graphic guide on the call website.

Who is eligible?

Individuals, legal entities and **consortia** established in a country or territory in the European Research Area. This includes the European Union, all overseas countries and territories linked to EU member states (Aruba, Bonaire, Curaçao, French Polynesia, French Southern and Antarctic Territories, Greenland, New Caledonia, Saba, Saint Barthélemy, Sint Eustatius, Sint Maarten, St Pierre and Miquelon), and all third countries associated to or currently negotiating an association agreement with Horizon Europe (for the 2023 iteration of the Call: Albania, Armenia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Faroe Islands, Georgia, Iceland, Israel, Kosovo, Moldova, Montenegro, Morocco, North Macedonia, Norway, Serbia, Tunisia, Turkey, Ukraine, United Kingdom). Please check the Guide for Applicants for more information.

Can individuals apply to IMPETUS?

Yes, individuals can apply, but they will be subject to additional checks before funding is released.

Can consortia apply to IMPETUS?

Yes. The funding is available to **consortia** established in a country or territory eligible to receive Horizon Europe grants. All consortium partners must be eligible, and one lead partner must submit the application, engage with IMPETUS, and distribute funds on behalf of the consortium. There is no minimum or maximum size for consortia, but they need to be appropriate to the amount of funding requested.

Submission

Can I submit more than one application for the same call?

You can participate in one application only, either on your own or as part of a consortium.

Does IMPETUS offer a pre-proposal check?

IMPETUS does not assess any applications prior to their submission. We are happy to answer general questions about the scope and format of the IMPETUS call via email or our social media channels, but we cannot make any statement about the feasibility or value of a proposal. The acceptance of a project will be at the discretion of the review panel.

I am new to this kind of funding; is there any extra help available?

Yes, we offer special support for new applicants. Please contact us on opencall@impetus4cs.eu by the end of January if you would like to be considered for this support. Your email should include a brief explanation of who you are and why you need this support. We will select ten applicants to participate in a dedicated webinar with the opportunity to ask questions and feedback on ideas. Note that this special support will not affect your chances of acceptance into the accelerator; we will provide feedback on ideas and concepts only, not on written applications.

Can I submit an application if I am already receiving funds from another programme?

The activities you plan to carry out with IMPETUS cannot receive double funding. Synergies with other sources of funding, including other Horizon 2020 or Horizon Europe projects, are encouraged as long as the grants are used for complementary, not overlapping purposes.

Can I submit documents that are not in English?

No. All documents submitted to IMPETUS must be in English. IMPETUS will not be able to accept any documents in other languages.

Responsible research and innovation

Who keeps the IP?

You will be the sole owner of the results and outcomes of your project, and all associated IP. However, we expect projects to follow an open approach, sharing results and experiences widely with the community. In addition, IMPETUS or the European Commission may ask you to present your work as part of our public relations and networking events, in order to showcase the benefits of the IMPETUS programme.

What happens with the data?

Applicants will have to be clear in their applications about what data that will be collected or generated through the project. For citizen science projects in which citizens will produce data to help with scientific inquiries, the application needs to include details about how data will be managed during and after the project implementation, including, if relevant, any GDPR concerns.

Do I need to share everything openly?

We will give preference to proposals that are committed to making their data and outputs available for reuse, following an open science approach. IMPETUS will support successful applicants to do so.

In addition, IMPETUS may require citizen science pilots funded through the programme to collect, manage and share data with the IMPETUS team. This may include the contributions of the citizens, as well as anonymised and/or aggregated data on citizen participation. Both are needed for the IMPETUS team to tailor their support and resources to provide support to projects in areas such as to data quality, motivating participation, citizen empowerment, diversity, public engagement, and impact.

What about ethics?

IMPETUS expects all successful applicants to the citizen science accelerator to abide by guidelines for ethical research. Most significantly, projects will be expected to ensure the informed consent of any human participants, who should be provided clear and concise instructions on what is expected of them, what personal or sensitive data will be gathered about them and how they can request the deletion of this data. Moreover, we require all pilots to ensure adequate data protection practises are in place to securely store any data gathered by

or about volunteers including, but not limited to: pseudonymisation, anonymisation and aggregation of data; encryption and use of secure servers.

We expect applicants to outline their plans to ensure this in their proposal. In addition, IMPETUS will provide advice and support on dealing with these aspects throughout the accelerator.

Evaluation

How do you select applications?

We follow a four-step process:

1. Eligibility checks: IMPETUS checks if eligibility criteria are met. Proposals considered not eligible will not proceed to step 2 of the evaluation process.
2. Reviews and shortlist: Eligible proposals will be evaluated by at least two reviewers.
3. Interview: Shortlisted applicants will be invited to a remote interview with an expert panel.
4. Decisions: After the interview, the panel will decide whether to accept the applicant into the programme.

When will I know if I'm shortlisted?

By 6th April 2023

What will the interview consist of?

During the interview we will ask you to give a presentation of your application of no more than 10 minutes, followed by 15 minutes of questions from a panel.

How many people can participate in the interview?

There is no limit to the size of the team as long as the participants add to the discussions.

Will I receive feedback?

All applicants will receive comments from the reviewers on their application forms.

When will the interviews be?

All interviews will happen between 11th and 18th April. Please note that this is right after Easter. We plan to send out invitations by 6th April 2023, including a time slot for the interview.

Can I reschedule the interview?

Unfortunately, we will not be able to negotiate interview dates and related conditions with the applicants and may not answer any queries on the subject. If an applicant is not able to attend the interview, we will have to reject their application.

When will I know if my application was approved/rejected?

All applicants will be notified by 6th April whether they've been invited to interviews or not. Applicants who made it through the interviews will find the outcomes 20th April.

Can I change my application once submitted?

You can update your application and resubmit as many times as you wish up until the deadline. Only the last submission made before the call deadline will be reviewed.

Can I apply again if my application is not successful?

If your application is not successful in the first call, you will be able to submit an application for the next call. However, please note that each call will have different challenges, and a project that was suitable for one call may not be suitable for the next.

Applicants who were selected into an accelerator in any of the calls will not be able to apply a second time.

Costs, payments and legal

What funding is available per pilot?

Successful applicants will receive up to €20,000 in total, to complete their 6-month pilot. Kickstarting (new) projects will be eligible for up to 20,000€, sustaining (existing) projects will be eligible for up to 10,000€.

What can I spend the funding on?

The funding can be spent on salaries, equipment, consumables, travel, subcontracting to other entities, and indirect expenditure (calculated as 25% of the total direct costs), in accordance with Horizon Europe guidelines. ([See here for an accessible overview.](#))

More information on funding can be found in the Guide for applicants.

How are the payments scheduled?

Funds will be transferred in two stages – 50% at the beginning of the project, and the remaining 50% at the end with the completion of activities, upon achievement of the milestones and deliverables agreed during negotiations.

Is subcontracting allowed?

Applicants may subcontract some of their activities to other parties as long as they are also from a Horizon Europe eligible country. No indirect costs (overhead) can be charged on subcontracting costs. Note that we expect the applicant to carry out most of the tasks of the project themselves. Subcontracting cannot be used to carry out key tasks in the project.

What do I have to do to receive the final payment?

You will receive your final payment on the completion of the below activities:

- Implement a six-month project as agreed during the negotiation phase and specified in the contract;
- Attend training, webinars, and co-design workshops;
- Attend monthly update calls with advisor and / or other pilots;
- Attend the IMPETUS Aperitive meetings every other month;
- Provide a formal report outlining your activities at the mid-term point and end of the pilot;
- Provide a pictures, text, and a short video about your work to be shared on the IMPETUS website and social media channels;
- Present your project at events as and when possible – all projects should allocate a portion of their budget to outreach activities;
- Acknowledge IMPETUS funding, and conduct outreach activities about IMPETUS to your network;
- Participate in IMPETUS impact assessment activities, such as:
 - Complete an impact assessment canvas
 - Send at least one survey to your citizen scientists (or organize another process for data gathering from them)
 - Compile a quali-quantitative impact assessment report following the methodology described in the IMPETUS training
 - Answer a dedicated questionnaire and/or provide needed data about achieved impacts
- Attend an interview with and provide feedback to the IMPETUS team.

The accelerator

Where will the training take place?

- An initial workshop will take place online between 22nd and 26th May 2023, as part of the negotiation phase.
- Further training and support sessions will be offered on online meeting platforms such as Microsoft Teams or Zoom.

Should I account for training in my budget?

- No. We plan to hold all trainings and support sessions online.

Will I need to travel?

- You are not required to travel, but you can if you want to. We do not mandate any face-to-face events, but participants are strongly encouraged to include community engagement and outreach activities in their work plans. All projects will also be invited to attend annual Ars Electronica Festival, which will offer an opportunity to meet IMPETUS peers and the project team.

How much time will I need to spend on Accelerator activities?

- We recommend expecting 1-2 hour every week for engagement with IMPETUS, for training, mentoring, reporting, and other engagement activities.